

Figure 1: Gemini Director Jennifer Lotz describes constellations and shares their stories with Haa'heo elementary students. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard)

Journey Through the Universe Celebrates 16 Years (and Counting!)

Janice Harvey

The Journey Through the Universe (Journey) program celebrated 16 continuous years of astronomy education in Hawai'i in March of this year! With the support of community businesses and over 60 local and national astronomy professionals, NOIRLab's flagship outreach program, led by the Communications, Education & Engagement (CEE)-Hawai'i team, continues to inspire students to reach for the stars. This year, Journey educators visited 250 classrooms and held StarLab sessions in 10 Journey kindergarten classrooms. In addition, ten career panels at Hawai'i Island high schools and a presentation for the public on the future decade of astronomical discoveries were held at the University of Hawai'i at Hilo. A two-day teacher workshop with a focus on the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) is planned for the fall of 2020

(pending COVID-19 restrictions).

Journey Through the Universe has flourished on Hawai'i Island for the last 16 years thanks to the commitment of the Hawai'i Department of Education, the support of the local business community, and the contributions of our many volunteer astronomy educators and ambassadors. The program has expanded over time from one week of classroom visits to a year-long program. Although the majority of the classroom visits are still consolidated into one week, astronomy educators continue to visit classrooms throughout the year.

During Journey week, 2–6 March 2020, over 60 astronomy educators shared their passion for astronomy with over 6,000 local students of all ages. Thirteen schools in the Hilo-Wai'ākea complex area, four schools in North

Figure 2: Gemini astronomer Siyu Xu leads an activity on the relative distance of our planets with a class from Walakeawaena Elementary School. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard)

“ encourage our students to reach for the stars.

Hawai'i Island, and, for the first time, classrooms in Maui (part of a partnership with the National Solar Observatory) were part of the Journey through the Universe program in 2020. To prepare for these visits, astronomy educators attended an educational workshop with tested activities and lessons and a special guest appearance by the school district superintendent Esther Kanehailua.

The superintendent stated: “Because Journey has been around for 16 years we can speak of its success, and because of the astronomy educators continuing to partner with us, we can grow these STEM opportunities for students. Journey Through the Universe has become the inspiration and template for growing many of our STEM/NGSS programs. The NGSS framework is to act as the foundation for science education standards while describ-

ing a vision of what it means to be proficient in science. It emphasizes the importance of the practices of science where the content becomes a vehicle for teaching the process of science.”

NSF's NOIRLab takes very seriously our role as a member of local Hawai'i communities, specifically their education and outreach needs. For more information on the Journey Through the Universe program, visit www.gemini.edu/journey.

Note: Participation numbers referenced in this article reflect several cancellations by astronomy educators due to COVID-19. Originally over 300 classroom visits were scheduled, but over 50 were cancelled due to the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic.